

**Notes on the nomenclature of *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840):
a rectification and a new subspecies name
(Lepidoptera: Erebidae, Eublemminae)**

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Abstract – The erebid moth *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840) is a distinctive species of the Pannonian region. The species-group name *panonica* Freyer, 1840 is an incorrect original spelling what needs a rectification. This spelling has been forgotten until its appearance in the catalogue compiled by Robert W. Poole in 1989 for noctuid names and it is again in use. The other original spelling *pannonica* Freyer, 1840 is the correct one, what was in general usage until 1989. On the basis of voluminous literature references these spellings are discussed. The name *Eublemma pannonica ronkayorum* Fibiger, Zilli & Yela, 2010 is a junior homonym of *Eublemma ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002, therefore the replacement name, *Eublemma pannonica ronkayi nomen novum* is proposed for the junior taxon. With three figures.

Key words – Albert Kindermann, Christoph Freyer, Imre Frivaldszky, Pannonia, replacement name, Symmia, Friedrich Treitschke

INTRODUCTION

Working on the erebid moth *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840), a distinctive species of the Carpathian Basin discovered by Imre Frivaldszky (1799–1870), we found two nomenclatural anomalies to be resolved: (1) The current spelling of the name *Eublemma panonica* needs rectification; and (2) the name *Eublemma ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002 is a senior secondary homonym of the subspecies *Eublemma panonica ronkayorum* Fibiger, Zilli & Yela, 2010, and needs a replacement name. The aim of the present paper is to discuss these subjects.

Abbreviations – HNHM = Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary); ICZN – International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION OF ZOOLOGICAL NOMENCLATURE 1999); ZMUC = Zoological Museum of University Copenhagen (Denmark).

NOMENCLATURE

Eublemma pannonica (Freyer, 1840)
(Figs 1–3A,B)

Anthophila panonica Frivaldszky – FREYER 1840: 67, 165; HEYDENREICH 1851: 47; POOLE 1989: 390 (unavailable, incorrect original spelling ICZN Art. 32.4).

Anthophila pannonica Frivaldszky – FREYER 1840: caption for table 330, figures 2, 4; EVERSMAAN 1844: 338.

Anthophila kindermanni – BOISDUVAL 1840: 174 (junior subjective synonym).

Anthophila lenis Eversmann – ANONYMUS [1842]: 4; EVERSMAAN 1844: 338.

Anthophila pannonica (Freyer) – LEDERER 1857: 43, 186.

Thalpochares pannonica (Freyer) – HORNIG 1858: 19; FRIVALDSZKY 1865: 98, 164, plate VII, fig. 12; AIGNER 1868: 60; HORVÁTH *et al.* 1875: 61; ABAFI-AIGNER *et al.* 1896: 40; STAUDINGER & REBEL 1901: 228; ABAFI-AIGNER 1907: 82, plate 51, fig. 23.

Autophila [!] *Pannonica*, Friv. – FRIVALDSZKY 1859: 26.

Micra lenis (Treitschke–Eversmann) – HERRICH-SCHÄFFER 1843: 440.

Micra pannonica (Freyer) – HERRICH-SCHÄFFER 1843: 440, in synonymy of *Micra lenis*; SPULER 1908: 289.

Porphyrinia pannonica (Freyer) – WARREN 1912: 265, pl. 51e “pannonica”; [KOVÁCS] 1950: 572; KOVÁCS 1955: 336; HRUBY 1964: 748; VARGA 1969: 54, fig. 63:1; GOZMÁNY 1970: 141, fig. 104B; FORSTER & WOHLFAHRT 1971: 252, pl. 26, fig. 37.

Eublemma pannonica (Freyer) – HACKER 1989: 330; VARGA 1989: 240; RÁKOSY 1996: 283, pl 6, fig. 13; RONKAY 1997: 63.

Eublemma panonica (Freyer) – FIBIGER & HACKER 1991: 34; VARGA 2010: 101; ANIKIN *et al.* 2017: 250; KOÇAK & KEMAL 2018: 221; SINEV 2019: 311.

Eublemma panonicum (Freyer) – KOÇAK & KEMAL 2018: 221; KEMAL *et al.* 2020: 29.

In the work of FREYER (1840) the species group name of this taxon is spelled as “Panonica” as the head entry of the description. This spelling is repeated in the table of contents, while the spelling for the figure caption is “Pannonica” (Fig. 1). Freyer did not present any etymology for the name, but attributed the authorship to “Frivaldszky” and indicated that the specimen he illustrated was collected in “Unterungarn” (Lower Hungary). This is a situation pertaining to ICZN Article 32.5.1. How can these two kinds of original spellings be explained? Freyer was the sole writer and illustrator of his own book series (OLIVIER 2000). However the layout was produced from his manuscript by the printer and the index was

prepared subsequently using the already existing sheets with page numbers. On the basis of this evidence the spelling “Panonica” is likely a printer’s error. This is supported by evidence that the other original spelling as “Pannonica” was Freyer’s own version, as Freyer himself drew and engraved all the illustrations by his own hands, including the caption for the figures as they appeared on the plates (Fig. 1B).

1A

1B

Figure 1. Extracts from the publication of Freyer (1840) evidencing two kinds of original spellings for the species-group name of the species *Eublemma pannonica*. A = The description of “Noct. Panonica” on page 67; B = figures 3 & 4 and their caption in plate no. 330; (words relevant for the present paper underlined by red) (source: Biodiversity Heritage Library)

The species was probably named after the collecting site of the type material. The collector of the first specimens was most probably Albert Kindermann Jr. (1810–1860), whose father Albert Kindermann Sr. (?–1847) sold this and other newly collected material to contemporary lepidopterists (LEDERER 1875, ABAFI-AIGNER 1899, OLIVIER 2000). One of his purchasers of Lepidoptera specimens was Imre Frivaldszky (1799–1870), of Pest (Hungary), who sent the newly acquired specimen to Freyer under the name “Pannonica”. Another client was Jean Baptiste Boisduval (1799–1879), of Paris (France), who described the species under the name *Anthophila kindermanni* and indicated the type locality as “Syrmia”. This may refer either to the settlement Sirmium (formerly: Szávaszentdemeter, county Szerém, Hungary; now Sremska Mitrovica, Serbia), or to the similarly named region, what is the southerly part of the former Roman province of Pannonia, and lies between the Danube and the Sava rivers. Indeed, in the 19th century, when Latin was still widely practiced, the southern (“lower”) part of the Hungarian Kingdom (at present shared by the countries Austria, Croatia, Serbia, Romania and Hungary) was associated with the former Roman province of Pannonia. It was never written with one “n”. The voluminous literature references listed above prove that the spelling “pannonica” was in constant and universal use, and was immediately emended, with the single exception of HEYDENREICH (1851). Although Kindermann collected the first specimens in Pannonia, the life history of the species was studied and examined in detail in the Great Pannonian Plain by I. Frivaldszky (FRIVALDSZKY 1859; FRIVALDSZKY 1865; ABAFI-AIGNER 1901; *c.f.* HORNIG 1858). In the HNHM there are two original Frivaldszky moths and one caterpillar specimen (Fig. 2).

POOLE (1989), in a bibliographical compilation of noctuid names and their sources, recorded the incorrect original spelling with the erroneous indication that there was no type locality. Since then, “panonica” started to reappear in the literature. FIBIGER & HACKER (1991) emphasised that *panonica* was “spelt with only one n at start”, without mentioning the other spelling in the original work of what became the common version in subsequent use. PARENZAN *et al.* (2002) stated, “Secondo Fibiger & Hacker, (1991) il nome corretto sarebbe *panonica*, come riportato in Poole (1989), ma lo stesso Freyer nel testo usa il nome *pannonica*, dalla regione Pannonia, che è stato erroneamente riportato come *panonica* nella tavola 330.” (in our translation = “According to Fibiger & Hacker (1991) the correct name would be *panonica*, as reported in Poole (1989), but Freyer himself in the text uses the name *pannonica* from the Pannonian region, which was erroneously reported as *panonica* in plate 330.”). Unfortunately Parenzan *et al.* mixed up the location of the two spellings in the original work and, in addition, made a false statement because Freyer did not write “Pannonian region” or anything similar in the text. Moreover, all of their considerations were connected to a specimen of *Eublemma cochylioides* (Guenée, 1852) misidentified as *E. panonica*.

2A

coll. E. Frivaldszky

2B

Figure 2. Museum specimens of *Eulemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840) with their labels from the Frivaldszky-collection. A = moth; B = caterpillar (same specimen in dorsal and lateral view) (scale bars = 1 cm)

VARGA (2010) stated in the English version of his notes presented for “*Eublemma panonica*” that in first revision of the species FIBIGER *et al.* (2010) had chosen “panonica” versus “pannonica” therefore the former one became the correct spelling. The meaning of the Hungarian version is somewhat different: “A faj nevét a [sic] Freyer a leírás során kétféleképpen betűzte („panonica” versus „pannonica”); a vonatkozó szabályok értelmében az első (ez esetben „hibás”) írásmód az érvényes (lásd Fibiger *et al.* 2010).” (in our translation = The name of the species was spelled differently by the [sic] Freyer in the original description (“panonica” versus “pannonica”); according to the relevant rules the first – in this case “erroneous” – spelling is the correct one (see Fibiger *et al.* 2010).” We do not know any rule which states that the first spelling should be the correct one among multiple original spellings. The ICZN Article 24.2.3 implies that the First Reviser is the author who cites all different spellings together and chooses one of them. This act was indeed made by PARENZAN *et al.* (2002), however, in the result of the misinterpretation of the original article and a misidentified specimen, as we noted previously.

And most recently in their papers some Turkish lepidopterists (KOÇAK & KEMAL 2018, KEMAL *et al.* 2020,) give the binomen *Eublemma panonicum*, using the incorrect original spelling of the species-group name as a neutral noun. The gender of the genus-group name *Eublemma* is feminine, therefore the usage of *panonicum* is erroneous (cf. ICZN Art. 30.2).

Eublemma pannonica ronkayi **nom. n.**
(Fig.3)

Eublemma pannonica lenis (Eversmann) – HACKER 1989: 330; BÁLINT, GUBÁNYI & KATONA 2014: 101 (misidentification).

Eublemma panonica ronkayorum – FIBIGER *et al.* 2010: 79, pl. 4, figs 29–32, unavailable; junior primary homonym (ICZN Article 57.2.), preoccupied by *Eublemma ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002; RONKAY 2014: 221.

The nominal species “*Anthophila lenis*” was described by EVERSMANN (1844) on the basis of an unstated number of specimens with the indication “Habitat circa Sareptam”. The name was attributed to Friedrich Treitschke (1776–1842) by the describer. The species was compared to “*Anth. pannonica* Frivaldsky – *Anth. Kindermanni* Boisd.”, stating that the size of the species was the same “*eadem magnitudine, qua praecedens*”. In the Treitschke collection drawer “HNHM-LEP-05718”, housed in the HNHM, there are two “*Anthophila*” specimens (one male, one female) under the curatorial label “*Lenis*”. These specimens were listed as “*Anthophila Lenis*” in the document published for the auction of the collection (ANONYMOUS [1842]). They most probably originated from the Kindermann brothers, who collected extensively in the Sarepta region

already before 1840 (ABAFI-AIGNER 1899). Treitschke identified these specimens representing an undescribed species, named the species and curated the specimens as such. Probably this was communicated to Eversmann by Treitschke himself or by the Kindermanns (see BÁLINT & ZOLOTUHIN 2017). Supposedly these specimens are *Anthophila lenis* syntypes but no evidence can be presented that these specimens have been seen indeed by Eversmann, or the description has been communicated by the Kindermanns or Treitschke on the basis of the specimens found at present in the Treitschke collection. Subsequently, *A. lenis* was considered as a synonym of *A. pannonica* by Frivaldszky, as the identification label on the male specimen “TREITS. [//] 2394.” testifies to this (Fig. 3A.). From the beginning of the 20th century to the present days the nominal taxon *lenis* was considered either as a variation of *E. pannonica* or *E. panonica* (STAUDINGER & REBEL 1905, WARREN 1912, FIBIGER *et al.* 2010) or a synonym of *E. panonica* (ANIKIN *et al.* 2017, SINEV 2019). The name was misapplied by HACKER (1989) in subspecies level for *E. pannonica*, and this very same taxon was described later as *E. panonica ronkayorum* in FIBIGER *et al.* (2010).

The nominal species *Eublemma ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002 has been described on the basis of the ZMUC holotype male (type locality: Turkmenistan, 20 km SE Bairmairm [= Bayramaly], 200–300m) and further 16 paratype specimens collected in Kazakhstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan (EBERT & HACKER 2002: 263–264). Eight years later the taxon *Eublemma panonica ronkayorum* has been established on the basis of the holotype male (ZMUC holotype male, type locality: Greece, Crete W, 4 km S Topolia, 350 m) (FIBIGER *et al.* 2010), and further 72 paratype specimens collected in Azerbaijan, Iran, Russia (Daghestan), Turkey, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. The two names represent two biological species (Figs 3B–C).

Both names are available having the same spelling as they have been established in combination with the same generic name, thus are primary homonyms (ICZN Article 53.3.) and hence the junior name is permanently invalid (ICZN Article 57.2.). It needs a substitute name as there is no available and potentially valid synonym for the taxon (ICZN Article 60.1.). Therefore we establish the new replacement name *Eublemma pannonica ronkayi* **nomen novum** for *Eublemma panonica ronkayorum* Fibiger, Zilli & Yela, 2010. The type material of *E. pannonica ronkayi* is that of what has been fixed for *E. panonica ronkayorum* (ICZN Article 67.8.) (Fig. 3).

The patronyms of the “ronkayorum” species-group names are the Ronkay brothers (the senior László and the junior Gábor), who study mainly the superfamily Noctuoidea and have described more than thousand species to date. The new replacement name refers solely to Dr László Ronkay, the elder brother, who was working in the HNHM Lepidoptera Collection for more than forty years, serving as lead curator between the period of 1994 and 2010.

3A

Anthophila lenis Eversmann, 1844
det. Zs. Bálint, 2014. I. 16

Magyar Természettudományi
Múzeum, Lászlógyűjtemény
Digitalizálva, 2014

3B

Turkmenistan, Kopet-Dagh Mts.
6 km S of Ispay-Kala, 1600 m,
57°07' E, 38°17' N,
16-23.VIII.1992, No. L74
leg. M. Hrabkay, Gy. László
and G. Ronkay

E. panonica
PARATYPE
ssp. ronkayorum
Fibiger, Zilli & Yela

3C

USSR, Turkmenia, Kara-Kum
desert, 100 m, 42 km N of
Ashkhabad, 58°33' E, 38°21' N,
15.10.1991, No. L45 leg.: A.
Podlussány, L. Ronkay & Z.
Varga

PARATYPE
Eublemma ronkayorum
Fibiger & Hacker, 2002

Figure 3. Museum specimens of *Eublemma* species with their labels from the Hungarian Natural History Museum, in dorsal view. A = *E. panonica* (Freyer, 1840) specimen curated as “*Anthophila Lenis*” in the Treitschke Collection (the identification label “*Pannonica*” was written by I. Frivaldszky); B = *E. panonica ronkayi* Katona, Tóth & Bálint, nom n. (paratype specimen of *E. panonica ronkayorum* Fibiger, Zilli & Yela, 2010); C = paratype of *E. ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002. (scale bars = 1 cm)

CONCLUSIONS

The spelling of *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840), an emblematic erebid moth species of the Pannonian fauna, has been stabilized via the citation of 37 literature references. The source of the various spellings was the original description, plus the purely technical cataloguing manner of Poole (1989), who reintroduced the original misspelling. According to FIBIGER *et al.* (2010) and SINEV (2019), the species *E. pannonica* is a Mediterranean-Asiatic represented by two subspecies: (1) ssp. *pannonica*, distributed from Mongolia (?) via the Kazakh-Russian steppe to the Carpathian Basin; and (2) ssp. *ronkayi*, from Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and the Caucasus (Dagestan), via NW Iran and Anatolia to the Mediterranean region, including Crete, and NW Africa (FIBIGER *et al.* 2010). The species *E. ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002 is an exclusively Central Asiatic species (EBERT & HACKER 2002).

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Jegyzetek az *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840) nevezéktanáról: helyesbítés és új alfaji név (Lepidoptera: Erebidae, Eublemminae)

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Összefoglalás – Az *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840) nevű bagolylepke a Pannon régió különleges faja. Az eredeti leírásban a fajcsoport-nevet kétféleképpen betűzte a szerző: (1) *panonica* és (2) *pannonica*. Az első változat egészen 1989-ig nem volt használatban, de az 1989-ben megjelent Robert W. Poole által szerkesztett Noctuidae katalógus után újra megjelent az irodalomban. Ezért helyesbítésre szorul. A másik, helyes névváltozat egészen 1989-ig volt általános használatban, amit a felsorolt irodalmi hivatkozások bizonyítanak. Az *Eublemma panonica ronkayorum* Fibiger, Zilli & Yela, 2010 név az *Eublemma ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002 fiatalabb társneve, ezért a fiatalabb taxon számára a behelyettesítő *Eublemma pannonica ronkayi* új nevet javasoljuk. Három ábrával.

Kulcsszavak – Freyer Christoph, Frivaldszky Imre, helyettesítő név, Kindermann Albert, Szerémség, Treitschke Friedrich

ÁBRAMAGYARÁZATOK

1. ábra. Részletek Freyer (1840) könyvéből, amelyek bizonyítják az *Eublemma pannonica* faj fajcsoport névének kétféle írásmódját. A = A „Noct. Panonica” leírása a 67. oldalon; B = A 330. színes tábla 3. és 4. képe, és az ábramagyarázatok (a cikk tárgyának szempontjából fontos szavak pirossal aláhúzva) (forrás: Biodiversity Heritage Library)

2. ábra. Múzeumi *Eublemma pannonica* (Freyer, 1840) példányok és céduláik a Frivaldszky-gyűjteményből (Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum). A = lepke (felülnézet); B = hernyó (ugyanaz a példány felül és oldalnézetből) (méretlécek: 1 cm)

3 ábra. Múzeumi *Eublemma* példányok és céduláik a Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum gyűjteményéből (mind felülnézetben). A = *E. pannonica* (Freyer, 1840) példány, a Treitschke-gyűjteményben „*Anthophila Lenis*” név alatt őrizve (a „Pannonica” határozó cédulát Frivaldszky Imre írta); B = *E. pannonica ronkayi* Katona, Tóth & Bálint, új név (az *E. panonica ronkayorum* Fibiger, Zilli & Yela, 2010 egyik paratípus példánya); C = az *E. ronkayorum* Fibiger & Hacker, 2002 egyik paratípus példánya. (méretlécek = 1 cm)